

Clinical Profile and Outcome of Covid-19 Intensive Care Patients with Nosocomial Infections: A Single-Centred Experience from India

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ABSTRACT

Background: Incidences of nosocomial infections in COVID-19 patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) have become a common occurrence. Hospital-acquired infections (HAI) present increased mortality, cost-of-care, especially relevant in multidrug resistant (MDR) infections. Our study aimed to assess the clinical implications associated with HAI-infected COVID-19 patients.

Patients and Methods: We conducted retrospective single-centred study on ICU-admitted adult COVID-19 patients for a year i.e., 2021-22 at a tertiary Indian institute and collated data of HAI epidemiological, clinical and microbiological reports.

Results: Rate of HIA at our centre was estimated to be 10.29% and the mortality rate was 40.4%. 10 different organisms (Bacteria: 8, Fungi: 2) were detected in HAI, of which the incidence of Gram-negative infections (GNI) was highest i.e., 60% and that of Gram-positive infections (GPI)/Fungi (Fungi infected) were 20% each. Mortality was highest among GPI (36.67%), FI (13.46%), followed by and GPI (7.69%). Tocilizumab treatment decreased the risk of survivability with no significant difference in the treatment outcomes.

Conclusion: This study provides a comprehensive picture of nosocomial infections characteristics among COVID-19 patients and provides insights regarding the impact of treatment on the outcome of these patients with suggestions for strategies. We found that critically ill patients with COVID-19 are at a high risk of developing HAI, especially MDR mediated CLABSI and CAUTI. Clinicians must therefore be cautious and mindful during implementing protocols for management of infectious complications with COVID-19 patients.

KEYWORDS: Hospital-acquired infection, COVID-19, multi-drug resistant, retrospective study, Tocilizumab

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HIGHLIGHTS

HAI, majorly contributed by MDR bacterial/fungal strains, add to the existing infection burden and treatment challenges in Covid inflicted individuals. Careful speculation and scrutinization should be exercised in treatment measure design in such sophisticated infection challenges to target and achieve reliable healthcare outcomes in already compromised individuals.

INTRODUCTION

Since its initial outbreak in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, the COVID-19 outbreak, caused by the novel severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2),

has spread globally and was declared a pandemic by WHO on 11th March 2020.1 The clinical presentation of this disease varies from asymptomatic to severe, fatal hypoxic pneumonia, thus leading to a rapid increase in the demand for intensive care and mechanical ventilation.2,3 In the past, several pandemics caused due to viral respiratory infections have resulted in nosocomial infections in acutely infected patients kept on mechanical ventilation support. Despite stringent infection control measures, nosocomial infections have been reported, and therefore, reducing the incidence of these infections remains a challenge.4 Moreover, these nosocomial infections account for a notable increase in intensive care unit (ICU) length of stay and increased risk of

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in-hospital mortality.⁵ As COVID-19 is a recent event, the analysis or the study on prevalence of nosocomial/hospital-acquired infections (HAI) among COVID-19 patients admitted to the ICU has been performed at several facilities^{6,7}; however, limited and inconspicuous knowledge of the concerned subject is available in the literature.

Antibiotics are usually preferred for disease management; however, the risk of co-infection in COVID-19 patients on ventilation support has resulted in the uncharted use of antibiotics eventually contributing in antimicrobial resistance spurt, thus urging the judicious use of antibiotics. Recent studies have demonstrated low rates of bacterial and fungal co-infections and superinfections in COVID-19 patients, ranging from 3 percent to 14 percent.⁸⁻¹⁰ Alternatively, several other studies have reported the incidences of secondary infection in 13.5 percent to 44 percent of COVID-19 patients admitted to the ICU.^{11,12} Some studies have reported fewer bacterial co-infections than secondary bacterial infections.^{13, 14.} Carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* is a type of pathogen that typically causes infections in healthcare facilities and has been considered as a potential public health concern during the times of COVID-19.^{15,16} Such instances of nosocomial fungal/ bacterial infections in Covid patients have been reported in Indian context as well, albeit not well-rounded. Therefore, clarity on the subject, that is, the characterization and prevalence of these infections is required, for scrutinized use of antibiotics and avoid their over utilization, risk of antimicrobial resistance and the occurrence of potential side effects, toxicity, and adverse events, which precipitates into greater mortality rates and inflating healthcare. Furthermore, Sogaard et al. have reported that hospital-acquired bacterial and fungal infections were higher among ICU patients (36.6 percent) than other patients (1.7 percent).¹⁷ Thus, in this retrospective study, we primarily aimed to assess the clinical features and outcomes associated with nosocomial infections in COVID-19 patients admitted to the ICU at a tertiary care hospital in India. This is a novel study wherein nuances about the outcomes among the Indian population have been presented.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This retrospective study was conducted at a tertiary healthcare facility in Mumbai, India, after the approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) (IEC Protocol No:- HNH/ IEC /2021/OCS/CCM /3).

Study design

The current study is a single-centered, retrospective, observational analytical study without any control group for COVID-19-positive cases. Additionally, IEC waived the requirement for written informed consent since the study only involved retrospective data analysis. Our study group included all adult patients (aged 18 years and above)

confirmed with SARS-Cov-2 infection using reverse transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) test conducted on nasal and pharyngeal swab specimens confirmed as per the WHO interim guidelines⁶ and admitted to the hospital for more than 24 hours within the study period for a years duration between March 2020-21. However, patients transferred from other facilities were excluded from the study. Data including epidemiological history, demographics, comorbidities, radiological assessments, laboratory findings upon admission, treatments, and clinical outcome concerning device-related and non-devices-related nosocomial infections were analyzed.

Study parameters

Data were retrieved from the medical health record system with regards to baseline demographic data, PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio at admission and time of intubation, comorbidities profile, previous hospitalization, oxygen therapy, High- frequency Nasal cannula, ventilation therapies in the form of invasive or non-invasive ventilation prone ventilation of COVID-19 patients were recorded (Table 1). Clinical characteristics such as time from the onset of symptoms to hospitalization, APACHE II score, and radiological investigation using high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) with CT severity index (CTSI) score were recorded. Microbiological investigations of HAI in COVID-19 patients admitted to the ICU were analyzed in accordance to hospital infection control committee protocol. Other clinical parameters, such as septic shock and gastrointestinal bleeding, were recorded in each patient. Treatment therapies were initiated as per the government task force COVID-19 treatment protocol. Antibiotics were provided per the hospital's antibiotics policy and stewardship recommendation, even during the follow-up.

Outcomes

The primary outcome measures were positive blood, urine, or tracheal aspirate cultures, body fluid cultures (others), and the classification of healthcare-associated infections per the hospital infection control policy. Secondary outcomes included patients with HAI with in-hospital mortality, ICU admission, use of non- invasive or invasive mechanical ventilation, total hospital length of stay, and ICU length of stay, all were considered while performing the analysis.

Statistical analysis

Categorical data were expressed as numbers and percentages. Chi- Square test was used for comparison of categorical variables. Fisher's exact test was employed instead of the χ^2 test when >20% of cells had expected frequencies <5. Continuous parameters were presented as mean \pm SD or median quartiles (25th/75th) wherein significance among groups was analyzed using Student's t-test or Mann Whitney U test, respectively. A two- tailed P-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses. All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS 21 (IBM

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SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 21.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp. IBM Corp. Released 2013).

RESULTS

Out of 505 COVID-19 patients admitted to the ICU of the hospital within the study period, 60 events of HAI occurred in 52 (10.29 percent), of which 8 were early HAI (within seven days of ICU admission). Out of these 52 patients, 60 percent survived the infection, and the rest, 40 percent, succumbed to the infection, hereon referred to as non-survivors.

Demographic & comorbidity characteristics

The median age of patients amongst the survivors was 70 years, and that amongst non-survivors was 73 years. There was no significant difference between the median age of survivors and non-survivors ($p = 0.526$). Further, the study population consisted of 38 males and 14 females. Among 38 males, 55 % of patients survived the HAI, and the rest 45 percent of patients succumbed to the HAI. Similarly, out of 14 female populations, 72 percent of patients were survivors, and 28 percent were non-survivors. Furthermore, no significant difference in comorbidities such as hypertension ($p = 0.613$), diabetes mellitus ($p = 0.870$), ischemic heart disease ($p = 0.700$), chronic kidney disease ($p = 0.281$), and obesity ($p = 0.449$) was observed between the two groups (Table 1).

Severity Index:

No significant difference was seen between the groups concerning the period from the onset of symptoms to hospitalization ($p = 0.618$). Additionally, there was no significant difference found in the PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio of patients recorded at the time of admission between the two groups (survivors and non-survivors) ($p = 0.957$). However, the PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio between the two groups of patients recorded at the time of intubation ($p = 0.041$) was statistically significant. Upon considering the severity scores, we found that non-survivors had high 136 APACHE II score [7.75 (10/12.25), $p = 0.173$] and CT severity index [20 (15.75/22), $p = 0.089$] as compared to their counterparts.

Treatment Variables:

The duration of oxygenation therapy via high-flow nasal cannula ($p = 0.197$), non-invasive ventilation ($p = 0.458$), non-rebreathing mask ($p = 0.574$), and prone positioning ($p = 0.465$) was noted between survivors and non-survivors and analysis showed lack of statistical significance. Further, 36 patients (69.23 percent) had to be intubated, of which 18 (i.e., 50 %) succumbed to the infection.

Outcome variables:

Out of 505 patients in the ICU study duration, 31 patients survived (60 %), whereas 21 patients (40%). The median (IQR) ICU length of stay (LOS) among survivors was 26 (22

days, whereas that among non-survivors was found to be 21 (19.5) days, suggesting that LOS in the ICU among non-survivors was shorter by 19.2 percent than among survivors. No significant difference in ICU LOS between the two groups was found ($p = 0.226$); however, a significant difference in total hospital LOS between the two groups was noted ($p = 0.007$), wherein non-survivors had shorter hospital LOS (36.7 %) than among survivors. Septic shock was observed among non-survivors (85.7 %) as compared to survivors (58 %) ($p = 0.064$). It was observed that 76.2 percent of deaths among non-survivors were on the account of septic shock. Lastly, gastrointestinal bleeding was observed in 14 patients (26.9 %), of which ten survived and four did not (Table 2).

1. Characterization of nosocomial infections

Predominantly, eight bacteria and two groups of fungi were identified as causative agents for the 60 events of HAI in 52 patients in our study population. We found that 64 percent of the patients who survived the infection were infected with a gram-negative bacteria (60 %), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (15 %), *Acinetobacter baumannii* & *Klebselia pneumoniae* (11 %), and *E. faecium* [Vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE), gram-positive bacteria] (11 %) followed by *Candida Auris* (10 %). On the other hand, 27 patients who succumbed to the infection were predominantly infected with gram-negative organisms such as *Acinetobacter baumannii* (7.6 %), *Klebselia pneumoniae* (7.6 percent), and fungi such as non-*Candida Auris* (7.6 percent). Upon further categorizing isolates into multi-drug resistant (MDR) or non-MDR strains, we found that MDR strains were identified in 51 samples; in contrast, only 11 samples were of non-MDR type. However, no significant difference in the distribution of MDR strains between survivors and non-survivors was observed ($p = 1.000$) (Table 3). Furthermore, 22 percent were identified with no devices-related HAI, while 78 percent were catheter/device-related. Among device-related infections, the incidence of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) was estimated to be 6.24/1000 ventilator days. In contrast, the incidence of catheter-associated urinary tract infections (CAUTI) was 3.61/1000 catheter days, and central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI) was 10.41/1000 line days.

2. Drug therapies used in infected COVID-19 patients

A high number of patients receiving Tocilizumab were non-survivors 57 percent compared to the survivors 43 percent; however, no significant difference in the treatment outcomes of the two groups was observed ($p = 0.135$). Interestingly, patients treated with Tocilizumab had more survivors, 56 percent, than non-survivors, 44 percent. However, similar to the Tocilizumab treatment outcome, no significant difference in the Tocilizumab treatment outcomes of the two groups was observed ($p = 1.000$). There was no significant difference in the distribution of patients receiving steroid treatment ($p = 0.269$). Moreover, patients receiving steroid treatments were

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mainly provided with dexamethasone, which may have proven effective, as 60.7 percent of patients survived and 40 percent failed to survive because of the infection. This trend was not picked up in patients receiving methylprednisolone and hydrocortisone. However, the efficiency of dexamethasone may also be attributed to the fact that it was administered for 15.5 days (median) to survivors as against five days (median) to non-survivors. Lastly, no significant difference in the treatment outcomes of antibiotics (BLBI, Carbapenem, and non- Carbapenem) and antifungals (fluconazole, Anidulafungin, Micafungin, Caspofungin, Posaconazole, amphotericin B, and Voriconazole) between survivors and non-survivors was observed (Table 4).

3. Strategies to reduce HAI (figure1 & 2)

Figure 1 shows the monthly incidence of HAI in our study population. A total of 60 HAI events were recorded among 52 patients. Of 60, 37 were MDR bacteria, followed by 11 non-MDR bacteria. The highest HAI incidences were reported in September (14) and October (11). 5 PRONG strategy was implemented to control the incidence of HAI post-October. The monthly HAI incidence rate declined; just 14 HAI cases were reported in the next five months. Figure 2 shows the HAI rates pre and post-5 PRONG strategy. Pre-5 PRONG strategy, the VAP infection rate was 6.19, slightly increasing to 6.39 in the post-5 PRONG. However, the CAUTI infection rate reduced from 4.03 to 2.57 post-5 PRONG implementation. A 36.22 percent decrease in CAUTI infection was observed. 197 Also, the CLABSI infection rate reduced from 11.79 in the pre-5 PRONG strategy to 7.70 in the post-5 PRONG. A 34.69 percent reduction was seen in the CLABSI infection rate post-5 PRONG implementation.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we investigated epidemiological features and risk factors associated with HAI and their outcomes in ICU patients affected with COVID-19 during the study period of one year at a tertiary care hospital. We found that almost 52 patients (10.29 %) acquired HAI, and the mortality rate was reported to be 40.4 percent. Khurana et al. have reported a slightly higher incidence of secondary infection (13 percent) with an in-hospital mortality rate of 33 percent.¹⁸ In a comparative analysis by He et al., notably higher mortality (15.4 percent) was reported among COVID-19 patients with HAI than those amongst COVID-19 patients without HAI (7.3 percent).¹⁹ Further, upon performing microbiological analysis, ten different organisms were detected in HAI; among these, 56 percent were Gram Negative bacteria. This finding is in accordance with the findings of Vincent et al., that reported the presence of Gram-negative microorganisms in majority than that of Gram- positive microorganisms in specimens collected from patients with HAI.⁵ Amongst Gram-negative bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 15 percent,

Acinetobacter baumannii 13 percent and *Klebselia pneumoniae* 12 percent were found to be the most common cause of HAI. On the other hand, amongst Gram-positive bacteria, *Enterococcus faecium* (VRE) 12 percent was found to be the most common cause of HAI. Similar studies have demonstrated the presence of Gram-negative bacteria (*Enterobacteriales*, *A. baumannii*, *P. aeruginosa*), with few other findings reporting the most common causative agents of HAI to be *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, *H. influenzae*, and *Klebselia sp.*, which is similar with the finding of our study.^{9-10,20} Another valuable finding with a potentially crucial clinical relevance is that MDR bacteria were identified in 85 percent of HAI. Out of 52 HAI-infected patients, 31 were infected with MDR strains, and the rest 21 patients were non- MDR with no considerable impact on the two groups. This outcome is probably due to prolonged use of broad- spectrum antibiotics, steroids, and COVID-19 inflammatory process leading to increased mucus production, impaired mucociliary clearance, and epithelial cell breakdown in addition to the lack of adherence to infection control measures because of understaffing and unexpected increased workload in the ICU during the pandemic. Furthermore, among device-related infections, we found that the incidence of ventilator- associated pneumonia (VAP) was 6.24 /1000 ventilator days, which is comparatively low as compared to the high incidence of VAP (28/1000 and 18/1000 ventilator days) found among critically ill COVID-19 patients in a similar study conducted by Maes et al. and Giacobbe et al.^{22,23} Similarly, in a study conducted by Meynaar et al.,²⁴ the incidence of CLABSI was estimated to be 6.25/1000 line days among COVID-19 patients, which is only slightly lower than the incidence of CLABSI (10.41 /1000 line days) estimated in the COVID-19 patients of our study group. Thus, we can say that the incidence of device-related infections in our study group was comparatively less than those documented in other literatures. Lastly, in our study, Tocilizumab was widely used as an immunomodulatory therapy and was found to be associated with an increase in mortality risk amongst HAI-infected COVID-19 patients. However, the difference between the survivability and non- survivability of patients was insignificant. Similarly, Guaraldi et al. ²⁵ reported increased co-infections among COVID-19 patients when treated with Tocilizumab, suggesting that Tocilizumab may not be the best treatment strategy for COVID-19-infected patients. Additionally, Chowdhary et al. have reported *Candida Auris* as the predominant causative agent of HAI among COVID-19 patients with a fatality rate of 60 percent, suggesting adverse outcomes for these patients.²¹

Strategies implemented to reduce HAI (Figures 1 & 2)

In order to curtail this increasing incidence of HAI among COVID-19 patients, stringent infection control measures were adopted. Besides the repetitive education sessions on the

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importance of hand hygiene, we also implement the following strategies: restricting the use of Carbapenem as part of antibiotic stewardship to prevent the rising resistance of Gram-negative bacteria²². We also introduced blue-colored glove surveillance, where healthcare personnel in the ICU were only allowed to use blue-colored gloves for bedside care and nowhere else in the unit; this was an attempt to prevent cross-contamination. Patients with MDR infections were cohorted separately to prevent the spread of MDR infections, and specialized, focused care was given to such groups of patients. In addition, environmental hygiene, especially for disinfection of high-touch surfaces carried out every 4 hours (Monitor knob, bed rails, door handle, etc.,) was done using higher concentration formaldehyde in rooms with patients harboring MDR bugs. Fungal infection and MDR bacteria tend to grow more rampantly with a high humidity factor in the ICU; we targeted a relative humidity of <60 percent was controlled with de-humidifier machines installed in the ICU.

LIMITATIONS

There were some limitations to our investigation. First, as it is a retrospective analysis of data collected primarily for clinical reasons in one of the COVID-19 hotspots, not all data were available for all patients. The current study was conducted in a single center in western India. It may be inappropriate to generalize and extrapolate the study findings to the entire population.

CONCLUSION

The current study provides a comprehensive look at not only the characteristics of nosocomial infections among COVID-19 patients but also provides insights regarding the impact of treatment on the outcome of HAI-infected COVID-19 patients and suggests strategies to control HAI infections. We found that critically ill patients with COVID-19 are at a high risk of developing HAI, especially CLABSI and CAUTI, frequently caused by MDR bacteria. Therefore, clinicians must undertake every effort to implement protocols for surveillance and prevention of infectious complications while treating COVID-19 patients. Thus to conclude, at our center, Gram-negative organisms such as *Pseudomonas*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Klebsella pneumoniae*, and fungi such as *Candida Auris* were equally responsible for mortality due to HAI and MDR contribution to this mortality was significant.

REFERENCES

- I. Xie M, Chen Q. Insight into 2019 novel coronavirus—An updated interim review and lessons from SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2020 May 1;94:119–124.
- II. Moolla MS, Reddy K, Fwemba I, Nyasulu PS, Taljaard JJ, Parker A et al. Bacterial infection,

- antibiotic use and COVID-19: Lessons from the intensive care unit. *South African Medical Journal*. 2021 Jun 1;111(6):575–581.
- III. Phua J, Weng L, Ling L, Egi M, Lim CM, Divatia JV et al. Intensive care management of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): challenges and recommendations. *The lancet respiratory medicine*. 2020 May 1;8(5):506–276-517.
- IV. Wee LE, Conceicao EP, Sim XY, Aung MK, Tan KY, Wong HM et al. Minimizing intra-hospital transmission of COVID-19: the role of social distancing. *Journal of Hospital Infection*. 2020 Jun 1;105(2):113–115.
- V. Vincent JL, Sakr Y, Singer M, Martin-Loeches I, Machado FR, Marshall JC et al. Prevalence and outcomes of Infection among patients in intensive care units in 2017. *Jama*. 2020 Apr 21;323(15):1478–14187.
- VI. Risa E, Roach D, Budak JZ, Hebert C, Chan JD, Mani NS et al. Characterization of secondary bacterial infections and antibiotic use in mechanically ventilated patients with COVID-19 induced acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Journal of Intensive Care Medicine*. 2021 Oct;36(10):1167–1175.
- VII. Vaughn VM, Gandhi TN, Petty LA, Patel PK, Prescott HC, Malani AN et al. Empiric antibacterial therapy and community-onset bacterial co-infection in patients hospitalized with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a multi-hospital cohort study. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2021 May 15;72(10):e533–541.
- VIII. Bassetti M, Kollef MH, Timsit JF. Bacterial and fungal superinfections in critically ill patients with COVID-19. *Intensive care medicine*. 2020 Nov;46(11):2071–2074.
- IX. Langford BJ, So M, Raybardhan S, Leung V, Westwood D, MacFadden DR et al. Bacterial co-infection and secondary infection in patients with COVID-19: a living rapid review and meta-analysis. *Clinical microbiology and infection*. 2020 Dec 1;26(12):1622–1629.
- X. Lansbury L, Lim B, Baskaran V, Lim WS. Co-infections in people with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Infection*. 2020 Aug 1;81(2):266–275.
- XI. Clancy CJ, Nguyen MH. Coronavirus disease 2019, superinfections, and antimicrobial development: what can we expect?. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2020 Nov 15;71(10):2736–2743.
- XII. Yang X, Yu Y, Xu J, Shu H, Liu H, Wu Yet al. Clinical course and outcomes of critically ill patients with SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a single-centered, retrospective, observational study.

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- The lancet respiratory medicine. 2020 May 1;8(5):475–481.
- XIII. Feldman C, Anderson R. The role of co-infections and secondary infections in patients with COVID-19. 301 302 *Pneumonia*. 2021 Dec;13:1–5. 303 304.
- XIV. Vaillancourt M, Jorth P. The unrecognized threat of secondary bacterial infections with COVID-19. *MBio*. 305 306 2020 Aug 25;11(4):e01806–01820. 307
- XV. Castro MG, Ubiergo L, Vicino M, Cuevas G, Argaraña F. Rising incidence of Carbapenem resistant isolates: an Argentinian hospital's experience. More trouble in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Iberoamerican Journal of Medicine*. 2022 Apr 12;4(2):92–99.
- XVI. Perez S, Innes GK, Walters MS, Mehr J, Arias J, Greeley R et al. Increase in hospital-acquired carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection and colonization in an acute care hospital during a surge in COVID-19 admissions—New Jersey, February–July 2020. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*. 2020 Dec 31 12;69(48):1827.
- XVII. Søgaaard KK, Baettig V, Osthoff M, Marsch S, Leuzinger K, Schweitzer M et al. Community-acquired and hospital-acquired respiratory tract infection and bloodstream infection in patients hospitalized with COVID-19 pneumonia. *Journal of Intensive Care*. 2021 Dec;9(1):1–10.
- XVIII. Khurana S, Singh P, Sharad N, Kiro VV, Rastogi N, Lathwal A et al. Profile of co-infections & secondary infections in COVID-19 patients at a dedicated COVID-19 facility of a tertiary care Indian hospital: Implication on antimicrobial resistance. *Indian journal of medical microbiology*. 2021 Apr 1;39(2):147–153.
- XIX. He Y, Li W, Wang Z, Chen H, Tian L, Liu D. Nosocomial infection among patients with COVID-19: A retrospective data analysis of 918 cases from a single center in Wuhan, China. *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology*. 2020 Aug;41(8):982–983.
- XX. Rawson TM, Moore LS, Zhu N, Ranganathan N, Skolimowska K, Gilchrist Met al. Bacterial and fungal co-infection in individuals with coronavirus: a rapid review to support COVID-19 antimicrobial prescribing. *Clinical infectious diseases*. 2020 Nov 1;71(9):2459–68.
- XXI. Chowdhary A, Tarai B, Singh A, Sharma A. Multidrug-resistant *Candida auris* infections in critically ill coronavirus disease patients, India, April–July 2020. *Emerging infectious diseases*. 2020 Nov;26(11):2694.
- XXII. Maes M, Higginson E, Pereira-Dias J, Curran MD, Parmar S, Khokhar F, Cuchet-Lourenço D, et al. Ventilator-associated pneumonia in critically ill patients with COVID-19. *Critical Care*. 2021 Dec;25(1):1–11.
- XXIII. Giacobbe DR, Battaglini D, Enrile EM, Dentone C, Vena A, Robba C, Ball L, Bartoletti M, Coloretti I, Di Bella S, Di Biagio A. Incidence and prognosis of ventilator-associated pneumonia in critically ill patients with COVID-19: a multicenter study. *Journal of clinical medicine*. 2021 Feb 3;10(4):555.
- XXIV. Meynaar IA, van Rijn S, Ottens TH, van Burgel ND, van Nieuwkoop C. Increased risk of central line-associated bloodstream infection in COVID-19 patients associated with dexamethasone but not with interleukin antagonists. *Intensive Care Medicine*. 2022 Jul;48(7):954–957.
- XXV. Guaraldi G, Meschiari M, Cozzi-Lepri A, Milic J, Tonelli R, Menozzi M et al. Tocilizumab in patients with severe COVID-19: a retrospective cohort study. *The Lancet Rheumatology*. 2020 Aug 1;2(8):e474–484.
- XXVI. The Impact of Antimicrobial Stewardship and Infection Control Interventions on *Acinetobacter baumannii* Resistance Rates in the ICU of a Tertiary Care Center in Lebanon; Nesrine A. Rizk, Nada Zahreddine, Nisrine Haddad, *Antibiotics*, July 2022; <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11070911>.

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Figure 1: Monthly HAI incidence

Figure 2: HAI rates pre and post-5 PRONG strategy

Table 1. Demographic and clinical data of HAI patients Table 2. Characteristics and severity of patients with HAI in COVID-19

	Survivors	Non-survivors	p-value
APACHE II ²	8 (6.00/12)	7.75 (10/12.25)	0.173
CTSI ²	14.5 (11.5/20)	20 (15.75/22)	0.089
Intubation ¹			
No	13 (41.94%)	03 (14.29%)	0.064
Yes	18 (58.06%)	18 (85.71%)	
HFNC (Days) ²	0(0/1)	0 (0/0.0)	0.197

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Covariates	Survivors	Non-survivors	p-value
NUMBER	31(59.6%)	21(40.3%)	
Gender¹			
Male	21 (67.74)	17 (80.95)	0.353
Female	10 (32.26)	04 (19.05)	
Age (Years)²	70 (59.00/78.00)	73 (62.50/80.00)	0.526
Time of symptoms onset to hospitalization²	4 (3.00/7.00)	5 (3.00/ 7.00)	0.618
Obesity¹			
No	25 (80.65)	19 (90.48)	0.449
Yes	06 (19.35)	2 (9.52)	
Hypertension¹			
No	14 (45.16)	8 (38.10)	0.613
Yes	17 (54.84)	13 (61.90)	
Diabetes Mellitus¹			
No	14 (45.16)	9 (42.86)	0.870
Yes	17 (54.84)	12 (57.14)	
Ischemic Heart Disease¹			
No	27 (87.10)	17 (80.95)	0.700
Yes	04 (12.90)	04 (19.05)	
Chronic Kidney Disease¹			
No	26 (83.87)	15 (71.43)	0.281
Yes	05 (16.13)	6 (28.57)	
Note: 1= Numbers and Percentages, 2 = Median and IQR			

Table 2. Characteristics and severity of patients with HAI in COVID-19

NIV (Days)²	2 (0/9)	3 (1/9)	0.458
O2 Therapy NRBM (Days)²	1 (0/5)	1 (0/4)	0.574
Prone (Days)²	2 (0/9)	0 (0/8.5)	0.465
P/F at admission¹			
≤100-1	15 (48.39)	10 (47.62)	0.957
>100-2	16 (51.61)	11 (52.38)	
P/F at Intubation¹			
Not intubated	13 (41.94)	3 (14.29)	0.041
≤100-1	14 (45.16)	17 (80.95)	
>100-2	04 (12.90)	1 (4.76)	
Admitted Elsewhere¹			
No	14 (45.16)	9 (42.86)	0.870
Yes	17 (54.84)	12 (57.14)	
LOS (ICU) (Days)²	26 (18/40)	21 (14.5/34)	0.226
LOS in Hospital (Days)²	34 (26/42)	21.5 (14.25/38.75)	0.007
Septic Shock¹			
No	13 (41.94)	03 (14.29)	0.064

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Yes	18 (58.06)	18 (85.71)	
GI Bleeding¹			
No	21 (67.74)	17 (80.95)	0.353
Yes	10 (32.26)	04 (19.05)	
Cause of Death - Septic Shock¹			
No	NA	05 (23.81)	
Yes	NA	18 (76.19)	
Multi-Drug Resistant¹			
No	6 (19.35)	5(23.80)	1.000
Yes	25 (80.64)	16 (76.19)	

Note: 1= Numbers and Percentages, 2= Median and IQR

Table 3. Distribution of microorganisms between survivors and non-survivors of HAI patients.

Sr.no	TYPE OF ORGANISM	CLABSI			CAUTI			VAP			BACTEREMIA			SUTI			Total	% incidences	Survived	% survival	Not-Survived	% non survival
		MDR	Non-MDR	Total	MDR	Non- MDR	Total	MDR	Non- MDR	Total	MDR	Non- MDR	Total	MDR	Non- MDR	Total						
Gram-negative Organism																						
1	Enterobacter Cloacae	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	5.00%	1	1.923076923	2	3.85%
2	Ac. baumannii	4	0	4	1	0	1	2	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	8	13.33%	4	7.692307692	4	7.69%
3	Pseudo aerugi	2	1	3	1	0	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	2	9	15.00%	8	15.38461538	1	1.92%
4	Escherichia coli	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	4	6.67%	3	5.769230769	1	1.92%
5	Klebselia Pneumoniae	2	0	2	0	0	0	3	0	3	1	0	1	1	0	1	7	11.67%	3	5.769230769	4	7.69%
6	Others	2	0	2	1	0	1	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	8.33%	1	1.923076923	4	7.69%
Total Gram negative		11	2	13	6	0	6	10	1	11	3	0	3	3	1	4	36	60.00%	20	38.46153846	16	30.77%
Gram Positive Organism																						
1	Enterococcus Faecium	0	1	1	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	6.67%	3	5.769230769	1	1.92%
1	E. Faecium (VRE)	1	0	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	2	7	11.67%	5	9.615384615	2	3.85%
2	E. fecalis	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1.67%	0		1	1.92%
Total gram positive		1	2	3	2	2	4	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	1	3	12	20.00%	8	15.38461538	4	7.69%
Fungal organisms																						
1	Candida auris	3	0	3	2	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	6	10.00%	3	5.769230769	3	5.77%
2	Non candida auris	2	1	3	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	6	10.00%	2	3.846153846	4	7.69%
Total fungal		5	1	6	2	0	2	2	0	2	1	1	2	1	0	1	12	20.00%	5	9.615384615	7	13.46%
Total Hai Events		17	5	22	10	2	12	12	1	13	6	1	7	6	2	8	60		33	63.46153846	27	51.92%

(CLABSI= Central line associated blood stream infection; CAUTI=Catheter associated urinary tract infection; VAP= Ventilator associated pneumonia; SUTI= ; VRE= Vancomycin resistant enterococcus)

Table 4. Pharmacological therapies used in HAI-infected COVID-19 patients

	Survivors	Non-survivors	p-value
Tocilizumab¹			
No	25 (80.65)	13 (61.90)	0.135
Yes	06 (19.35)	08 (35.00)	
Itolizimab¹			
No	26 (83.87)	17(80.95)	1.00
Yes	5 (16.13)	4 (19.05)	
Predominant steroid¹			
No	0 (0.00)	2 (10.00)	0.269
Dexamethasone	17 (60.71)	08 (40.00)	
Methylprednisolone	9 (28.57)	09 (35.00)	
Hydrocortisone	5 (10.71)	02 (15.00)	
Antibiotics			
Initial antibiotic¹			
No	13 (35.71)	4 (15.00)	0.188
Yes	18 (64.29)	17 (85.00)	
BLBI antibiotics¹			
No	5 (17.86)	1 (5.00)	0.379
Yes	11 (82.14)	20 (95.00)	
Carbapenems¹			
No	21 (75.00)	12 (60.00)	0.349
Yes	10 (25.00)	9 (40.00)	
Non-carbapenam¹			
No	9 (21.43)	3 (5.00)	0.214

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Yes	22 (78.57)	18 (95.00)	
Antifungals			
Flucanazole¹			
No	19 (64.29)	16 (70.00)	0.763
Yes	12(35.71)	5(30.00)	
Anidulafungin¹			
No	24 (75.00)	17 (75.00)	1.000
Yes	7 (25.00)	4 (25.00)	
Micafungin¹			
No	27 (85.71)	16 (80.00)	0.703
Yes	9 (14.29)	5(20.00)	
Caspofungin¹			
No	24 (82.14)	15 (80.00)	1.00
Yes	7 (17.86)	6(20.00)	
Posaconazole¹			
No	30 (96.43)	17 (85.00)	0.294
Yes	1 (3.57)	4 (15.00)	
Amphotericin b¹			
No	29 (92.86)	18 (85.00)	0.636
Yes	2 (7.14)	3 (15.00)	
Voriconazole¹			
No	29 (92.86)	21 (100.00)	0.504
Yes	2 (7.14)	0 (0.00)	
Note: 1= Numbers and Percentages, 2= Median and IQR			